

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Nathalie Rathkamp (2025): Review of Mark R. Beissinger (2022): Revolutionary Episodes Dataset (published on Discuss Data), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/6C6409AE-5BB8-48B2-97B4-2CB5AA5DDB5B>

Abstract

The Revolutionary Episodes Dataset was created by Mark R. Beissinger and lists 345 revolutionary episodes in the time period from 1900 to 2014 from around the world (1). The research team defined a revolutionary episode as “a mass siege of an established government by its own population with the aim of displacing the incumbent regime and substantially altering the political or social order.” (Beissinger 2022: 5). Each of these revolutionary episodes do however require a peak mobilization of at least 1.000 civilian participants to be included in this dataset (Beissinger 2022: 10). Of the 406 total entries in this dataset, there are 30+ events listed for the countries of Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia covered by Discuss Data. According to Beissinger the plan is to update and revise the dataset in future iterations (Beissinger 2022: 13). The data review contains a link leading to the official Revolutionary Episodes Dataset website from which both the dataset, the codebook and additional information are available as a free download.

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Data Review – Revolutionary Episodes Dataset

The Revolutionary Episodes Dataset was created by Mark R. Beissinger and lists 345 revolutionary episodes in the time period from 1900 to 2014 (1). The research team defines a revolutionary episode as “a mass siege of an established government by its own population with the aim of displacing the incumbent regime and substantially altering the political or social order.” (Beissinger 2022: 5). Each of these revolutionary episodes do however require a peak mobilization of at least 1.000 civilian participants to be included in the dataset (Beissinger 2022: 10).

Revolutions are usually characterized by situations of competing sovereignties, however this dataset also includes those where no clear alternative to the current regime emerges, since subjecting a regime to a state of siege in order to displace it is a sufficient indicator of its citizens rejecting that governments right to rule (Beissinger 2022: 6). Furthermore, anti-colonial and separatist mass sieges of power aimed at attaining state independence are also included, since these seek to create a separate national state, thus altering the character of the national government which they were governed by (Beissinger 2022: 9).

On the other hand, ‘non-revolutionary’ cases, meaning cases that lack a focus on overthrowing the national government, were not included in the dataset. This includes: (a) rebellions that aim to defend local autonomy against incursions by central government, (b) irredentist conflicts that seek to detach a particular territory from one state and place it within the boundaries of another, (c) resistance to an immediate foreign invasion, (d) instances of resistance to the immediate imposition of colonial rule, and (e) instances of foreign-imposed regime-change (Beissinger 2022: 9-10).

The dataset draws its information from a large variety of sources. These sources include: “eight published encyclopedias, nine existing global datasets on wars, civil wars, ethnic conflict, and instances of nonviolent resistance, nine online encyclopedias and databases of conflict events, and all files of Keesing’s World News Archive from 1931 to the present [...]. Moreover, 135 other occasional sources (newspapers, websites, and online encyclopedias) and over eight hundred scholarly books and articles were consulted on specific episodes in order to identify whether an episode qualified for inclusion.” (Beissinger 2022: 11-12).

During the identification process short narratives were written on each potential case and discussed in weekly meetings of the research team, where they would decide whether a case fit the inclusion criteria or not (Beissinger 2022: 12). In total 345 episodes were included, however those that came close to inclusion but did not make it because of one reason or another are also available to view in the excluded cases datasheet (Beissinger 2022: 12).

The data in this dataset is organized into spreadsheets which are structured into four parts: A) the main datasheets, B) the relational datasheets, C) the coding datasheets, and D) the

excluded cases datasheets (Beissinger 2022: 4). These datasheets in turn focus on the following:

Ten main datasheets that each address one of the following:

- 1) “the timing (start and finish) of revolutionary contention and its territory allocation;
- 2) the goals of rebellion as articulated by revolutionary oppositions;
- 3) the forms of contention (locations and tactics);
- 4) the features of incumbent regimes on the eve of revolutionary contention;
- 5) information on the peak size of participation and the composition of key participants;
- 6) patterns and phases of rebellion, the character of opposition leadership, and the forms of media used by the opposition;
- 7) violence and deaths during revolutionary contention;
- 8) types of relationships with other revolutionary episodes (diffusion, recursion, reversal of a prior episode, or other);
- 9) the outcomes of revolutionary contention;
- 10) hyperlinks to a separate file containing short narratives of the events of each episode, with notes on the episode and the episode’s summary classification” (Beissinger 2022: 4).

Five relational datasheets that each address one of the following:

- 1) “raw death estimates for each episode, as drawn from secondary sources;
- 2) the grievances articulated by revolutionary oppositions, as drawn from secondary sources;
- 3) prior episodes related to each episode;
- 4) hyperlinked sources consulted on each episode and
- 5) print sources consulted on each episode (The list of sources is not exhaustive)” (Beissinger 2022: 4).

Ten coding datasheets that each address one of the following:

- 1) “modified COW (Correlates of War) codes for each country or territory;
- 2) codes for different types of incumbent governments;

- 3) codes for the first movers in revolutionary contention;
- 4) codes for the actions that began revolutionary contention;
- 5) codes for the actions that ended revolutionary contention;
- 6) codes for different patterns of revolutionary contention;
- 7) codes for types of opposition leadership;
- 8) codes for the types of relationships between episodes;
- 9) codes for the names of specific transnational waves of revolution to which episodes might belong;
- 10) codes for the specific grievances articulated in revolutionary contention.” (Beissinger 2022: 4-5).

Four excluded cases datasheets that each address one of the following:

- 1) “the location and timing of the episode and the reasons for its exclusion;
- 2) a short narrative describing the episode and the reasons for its exclusion (the narratives are located in a separate file that is hyperlinked to the dataset);
- 3) hyperlinked sources consulted on each episode (organized relationally around the excluded episode id number altrevid);
- 4) print sources consulted on each episode (also organized relationally around the excluded episode id number altrevid)” (Beissinger 2022: 5).

Beissinger states that: “To take full advantage of the information in these relational fields, the fields can be connected to the main datasheets in MS Excel using VLOOKUP or PowerPivot, or the data can be exported to a relational database program such as MS Access.” (Beissinger 2022: 4). For an exhaustive list of the coded variables please refer to Beissinger 2022: 19ff.

Discuss Data relevant country coverage:

Country	Entries
Azerbaijan	2
Belarus	1
Estonia	1
Georgia	3
Kyrgyzstan	2
Latvia	1

Lithuania	1
Moldova	1
Russia	9
Tajikistan	1
Ukraine	2
USSR	10

Sources:

- (1) Beissinger, Mark. Revolutionary Episodes Dataset. [Revolutionary Episodes Dataset | Mark R. Beissinger \(princeton.edu\)](#). Last accessed 30.09.2024.
- (2) Beissinger, Mark R. 2022. *The Revolutionary City: Urbanization and the Global Transformation of Rebellion*. Princeton: Princeton University Press. Version 1.0. https://www.dropbox.com/scl/fi/vy6ibp9ggmjmmjye4brys/Revolutionary-episodes-dataset_v_1.0.zip?dl=0&e=1&file_subpath=%2FData+description.pdf&rlkey=2kp5ujvwq5augdtgaws10dc2y. Last accessed 30.09.2024.